

Reaction of Some *gem*-Dihalides with 1,4-Dilithiooctaphenyltetrasilane and 1,5-Dilithiodecaphenylpentasilane

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An attempt has been made to utilise 1,4-dilithiooctaphenyltetrasilane and 1,5-dilithiodecaphenylpentasilane for the preparation of tetrasilacyclopentane and pentasilacyclohexane respectively by their reaction with some *gem*-dihalides. These reactions did not in any case give the expected cyclic products. Tetraphenylethylene, octaphenylcyclotetrasilane (Compound A), decaphenylcyclopentasilane (Compound B) were isolated from the reaction of 1,4-dilithiooctaphenyltetrasilane with dichlorodiphenylmethane. When the same *gem* dihalide is treated with 1,5-dilithiodecaphenylpentasilane-tetraphenylethylene, decaphenylpentasilane-1,5-diol and Compound B were isolated. Decaphenylpentasilane-1,5-diol, and Compound B were the reaction products characterised when CH_2Cl_2 , CH_2Br_2 , and $\text{MeC}(\text{Cl})_2\text{Me}$ were treated separately with 1,5-dilithiodecaphenylpentasilane. Only with CH_2Cl_2 , in the above reactions, 1,5-dimethyldecaphenylpentasilane was isolated as an additional product. A plausible mechanistic path leading to the formation of the above products are suggested.

MANY silacycloalkanes are known in which silicon is bonded to two carbon atoms in the cyclic system¹. Cyclic carbosilanes² provide examples where carbon is bonded to two adjacent silicon atoms in a ring system.

Lithium cleavage of the perphenylated cyclosilanes, octaphenylcyclotetrasilane (Compound A) and decaphenylcyclopentasilane (Compound B)³ in tetrahydrofuran (THF) has provided a facile route to the corresponding α , ω -dilithioperphenylated polysilanes, 1,4-dilithiooctaphenyltetrasilane (I)⁴ and 1,5-dilithiodecaphenylpentasilane (II)^{5,6} respectively. In the present investigation, an attempt was made to utilize the dilithio intermediates (I) and (II) for the preparation of tetrasilacyclopentanes and pentasilacyclohexanes (III), respectively, by their reactions with some *gem*-dihalides :

The reactions of (I) with dichlorodiphenylmethane and of (II) with dichlorodiphenylmethane, dichloromethane, dibromomethane and 2,2-dichloropropane did not in any case give the expected cyclic products corresponding to (III). The products actually obtained are listed in Table I and some typical reactions are described in the experimental section.

From the reaction of (I) with dichlorodiphenylmethane there were obtained tetraphenylethylene, Compound A, Compound B and viscous polymeric material. The formation of tetraphenylethylene in this reaction

and in the corresponding reaction of (II) and dichlorodiphenylmethane may be explained in several ways, one of which is by an intermediate carbene formation :

and another is by coupling of the intermediate organolithium species (IV) :

The formation of a small amount of Compound B, in the reaction of (I) with dichlorodiphenylmethane, is expected, according to the previous observation of the cleavage reactions of octaphenylcyclotetrasilane with lithium⁴, organolithium⁵, and organosilyllithium⁵ reagents. 1,4-dilithiooctaphenyltetrasilane formed by the initial lithium cleavage of octaphenylcyclotetrasilane is able to cleave more octaphenylcyclotetrasilane. Also cleavage of the α , ω -dilithio compound (V) by lithium can increase the variety of disilanyl lithium compounds³. It was reported that decaphenylcyclopentasilane^{3,5,6} (Compound B) was isolated in 18% yield when octaphenylcyclotetrasilane is cleaved by phenyllithium in THF-ether mixed solvent system. The greatly enhanced reactivity of octaphenylcyclotetrasilane over decaphenylcyclopentasilane can be accounted for by the relative ease of formation of a pentavalent intermediate^{3,6}. The plausible explanation of the formation of Compound B in the above mentioned reaction may be formulated by (i) intra molecular cyclization or by

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TABLE 1—REACTION OF 1,4-DILITHIOOCTAPHENYLTETRASILANE(I) and 1,5-DILITHIODECAPHENYLPENTASILANE(II) with *gem*-DIHALIDES.

Li(SiPh ₂) _n Li n=	R ₂ CX ₂	Mole ratio, I : R ₂ CX ₂ II : R ₂ CX ₂	Products ^{a,b}		Other products (%)	
			Compound A(%)	Compound B(%)		
4	Ph ₂ CCl ₂	1:1.5	17.6	4.4	Tetraphenylethylene;	20
5	„	1:1.6	—	45.7	Tetraphenylethylene	34.6
5	CH ₂ Cl ₂	1:3	—	34	HO(SiPh ₂) ₅ OH,	7.3
5	CH ₂ Br ₂	1:2	—	24.7	Me(SiPh ₂) ₅ Me,	2.1
5	MeCCl ₂ Me	1:1.5	—	56	HO(SiPh ₂) ₅ OH,	0.7
					HO(SiPh ₂) ₅ OH,	5.2
					HO(SiPh ₂) ₅ OH,	3.3

^a The yield of tetraphenylethylene was calculated on the basis of dichlorodiphenylmethane.
^b The remainder of the reaction residue in all cases consisted of an unidentified polymeric material.

(ii) helogen-metal interconversion and lithium-halide elimination sequence. **Experimental**

This mechanism should lead to other cyclic or linear polysilanes, but no such compounds were characterized in the above mentioned reaction.

The formation of Compound B and decaphenylpentasilane-1,5-diol in the reaction of (II) with R₂CX₂ (R = Ph, Me or H; X = Cl or Br), may be explained by a similar halogen-metal interconversion and lithium halide-elimination sequence :

Formation of 1,5-dimethyldecaphenylpentasilane in the reaction of (II) with dichloromethane has an analogy in a similar reaction of triphenylsilyllithium with this halide. It has been reported⁷ that one of the products in this reaction was methyltriphenylsilane formed probably according to the following scheme :

In a similar manner, each terminal-SiPh₂Li groups in (II) may be converted to-SiPh₂Me end groups to afford 1,5-dimethyldecaphenylpentasilane.

All reactions were carried out under an atmosphere of dry, oxygen-free nitrogen. The THF was dried over sodium wire and distilled from lithium aluminium hydride immediately before use. Products were, in general, characterized by a comparison of physical data with those of authentic specimens. The petroleum ether used had b. p. 60°-70°.

Reaction of 1,4-dilithiooctaphenyltetrasilane (I) with dichlorodiphenylmethane :

A solution of (I), obtained by the lithium cleavage of Compound A (22 g., 0.03 mole) in THF was added to a stirred solution of dichlorodiphenylmethane (10.66 g., 0.045 mole) in THF (100 ml.). After stirring the coloured solution for 36 hr., Colour Test I⁸ was negative. The reaction mixture was hydrolysed, the hydrolysate extracted with ether and the organic layer filtered to give Compound A (4 g., 17.6%). Evaporation of filtrate afforded a resinous material. This was triturated with boiling petroleum ether, cooled and filtered to give Compound B (1 g., 4.4%). The petroleum ether filtrate was concentrated and the residue chromatographed over neutral alumina to afford tetraphenylethylene (1.5 g., 20%), m. p. and mixed m. p. 225°-227°.

Reaction of 1,5-dilithiodecaphenylpentasilane (II) with dichlorodiphenylmethane :

A solution of (II) (0.028 mole), prepared by the lithium cleavage of Compound B (27.3 g., 0.03 mole) in THF, was added slowly to a stirred solution of dichlorodiphenylmethane (10.66 g., 0.045 mole) in THF (100 ml.). After 36 hr., the coloured reaction mixture gave a negative Colour Test I. Hydrolysis, extraction with ether and filtration gave Compound B (6 g.). Removal of the solvent from the filtrate left a resinous material. This was boiled with petroleum ether, cooled and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and the residue crystallised from benzene-ethanol to give tetraphenylethylene (2.6 g., 34.6%), m. p. and mixed m. p. 224°-226°. The petroleum ether-insoluble material was triturated with boiling acetone, cooled and filtered to give Compound B (6.5 g.; total yield of Compound B : 12.5 g., 45.7%). The concentrated filtrate deposited a solid on cooling. Crystallization of the latter from benzene-petroleum ether gave decaphenylpentasilane-1,5-diol⁹ (2.2 g., 7.3%), m. p. and mixed m. p. 170°-172°.

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